

Short name	Business models	Long name	Development of business models that encourage investment in CCS
Geographical scope	Across all regions		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>CCS does not produce a ‘product’ in the traditional sense, so it requires government intervention to make it happen: this can be in the form of government ownership of projects, regulatory requirements, government funding or other measures (see GCCSI 2019¹ for more detail). Different approaches have their merits, but no country has yet found one that drives investment in CCS in the long term (after the end of any initial subsidy period / government investment) and prevents ‘carbon leakage’ from high-emitting industries moving overseas. Carbon capture and storage can represent a very significant cost-increase with varying shares of output between industries: high capture rate CCS add anywhere from +60% to +100% to the cost of making cement.^{2,3}</p> <p>Specific issues include:</p> <p>The need to mitigate and underwrite cross-chain risks, which are particularly high for first-of-a-kind projects.</p> <p>The need for financial security to underwrite CO₂ storage permits.</p> <p>How to address both supply and demand: demand mechanisms could include certification of low-carbon products, accompanied by public procurement rules that require low-carbon materials to be used in major projects; alternatively, governments could set standards for carbon intensity of products.</p> <p>The risk of carbon leakage due to emissions standards or a high carbon price (such as in the EU ETS) can be mitigated by a carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM) such as is being developed by the European Commission⁴. The EU CBAM will initially apply to cement, iron and steel, aluminium, fertilisers, electricity and hydrogen, and the transitional phase is due to begin in October 2023. The phasing in of the CBAM will align with the phasing out of free allocations in the EU ETS.</p>		

¹ GCCSI (2019) *Policy Priorities to Incentivise Large Scale Deployment of CCS*. Available at: <https://www.globalccsinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/TL-Report-Policy-options-for-CCS-investment-digital.pdf>

² IEA. (2020a). *Energy Technology Perspectives 2020*. Energy Technology Perspectives. <https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-technology-perspectives-2020>

³ Kearns, D., Liu, H., & Consoli, C. (2021). *Technology Readiness and Costs of CCS*. <https://www.globalccsinstitute.com/resources/multimedia-library/technology-readiness-and-costs-of-ccs/>

⁴ https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/green-taxation-0/carbon-border-adjustment-mechanism_en

<p>Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)</p>	<p>Stakeholders surveyed agreed that enabling all players to make a good business case was crucial. They suggested a number of ways of achieving this:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having clear economic incentives to realize projects. • EU or country level funding mechanisms • More programs, and with higher budget, like Horizon Europe, the Connecting Europe Facility and the EU ETS Innovation Fund. • Country or EU level compensation mechanisms must be put in place to mitigate the business exposure of the different parties in the value chain if another party underperforms. • Dedicated funding for each project scope. The need for integrated projects, with multiple players, hampers access to funding • Temporary incentives / funding of the gap between CO2 taxes and cost of CCUS • Access to low-cost capital • Massive subsidizing scheme for shared CO2 infrastructure • Allow and promote state-aid for the development of infrastructure. <p>Promotion of carbon contracts for difference (CCfDs).</p> <p>Certainty is another important ask: stakeholders also wanted greater certainty on the price of CO₂ to be able to demonstrate a viable business case for investment in CCS projects; they also raised the issue that a change in government can mean changes to subsidy regimes, which make a long-terms business case risky. This raises the importance of cross-party political support for CCUS developments, as well as the importance of subsidy regimes in the form of contracts rather than tax credits or similar incentives, to allow certainty over future income.</p> <p>As well as the funding for projects, stakeholders raised the issue of partnership and ownership structures within projects.</p>
<p>Other issues this affects</p>	<p>Complexity of the CCUS value chain</p>
<p>References</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global CCS Institute (GCCSI); (2019): Policy Priorities to Incentivise Large Scale Deployment of CCS, https://www.globalccsinstitute.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/TL-Report-Policy-options-for-CCS-investment-digital.pdf, Australia. • IEA; (2020a): Energy Technology Perspectives 2020, https://www.iea.org/reports/energy-technology-perspectives-2020, France. • Kearns, D., Liu, H., & Consoli, C.; (2021): Technology Readiness and Costs of CCS, https://www.globalccsinstitute.com/resources/multimedia-

	<p>library/technology-readiness-and-costs-of-ccs/, Australia.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• European Commission; Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism, https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/green-taxation-0/carbon-border-adjustment-mechanism_en, Belgium.
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